

Multi-Configuration Optimization of the Multi-group Energy Structure for Lead Fast Reactor simulations

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ABSTRACT

The identification of an appropriate energy group structure is a key step in accurately collapsing group constants for full-core transient and multiphysics analyses, as it directly impacts both the accuracy and computational efficiency of multi-group calculations. Genetic Algorithms (GAs) have proven to be effective tools for solving such high-dimensional, non-linear optimization problems. By emulating the Darwinian principle of natural selection, they aim to identify a nearly-optimal, coarser energy grid through physics-informed objective (fitness) functions. In this study, physics-based fitness functions associated with relevant full-core parameters were implemented in the optimization framework, extending previous works in literature. The GA was applied to simultaneously optimize the energy group structure for three different core configurations of the NEA Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR) benchmark, using the neutronic module of the FRENETIC code coupled with Serpent 2 Monte Carlo simulations. The results indicate that the constraints imposed by the simultaneous optimization reduce the solution space, leading to similar optimized structures across configurations, with variations observed only for a few energy boundaries.

Keywords: Lead-cooled Fast Reactor, multi-group, genetic optimization, energy-collapsing, Genetic Algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION

The identification of a proper energy group structure to collapse the group constants for full-core deterministic simulations to be employed in full-core transient and multiphysics analysis is still a relevant research topic in reactor physics [1, 2], as it strongly affects the accuracy and reliability of the results.

Indeed, the energy structure must be identified with the intention of preserving the physical features of the problem while minimizing as much as possible the computational effort. These requirements are more likely to be met when both the number and the distribution of the energy groups are optimised. This optimisation problem is stiff and non-linear, and its complexity increases when dealing with fast spectrum systems [3].

In this framework, optimization techniques, and in particular Evolutionary Algorithms (EA), can play a key role, as they aim at identifying a nearly optimal solution, starting by a set of feasible ones and by using proper physics-driven objective functions. Among the several branches of EA, Genetic Algorithms (GA) are the best known and they have already been tested to optimize the energy structure of, for instance, Molten Salt Reactors (MSR) [4],[5]. Also, GAs have been recently applied to the Advanced Lead Fast Reactor European Demonstrator (ALFRED) design, proposed and developed within the LEADER project. At first, the optimization technique was employed to identify a set of optimal solutions with a number of energy groups defined *a priori* [6], which was tested comparing the deterministic multi-group calculations with reference Monte Carlo results. Then, in a follow-up work [7], the GA routine

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was streamlined and its structural constraints relaxed, enabling it to naturally determine the number and distribution of the optimal energy boundaries. Fitness Functions (FFs) were rigorously defined on a physical basis, offering a more comprehensive insight into the differences between the performances of the optimised solution and the reference Monte Carlo evaluation [8]. Both studies considered a single operational configuration of the reactor.

Building on the promising outcomes of the previous studies, in view of future time-dependent full-core analyses, this work aims at extending the GA application to identify a group structure that is appropriate for three different reactor operational configurations at the same time, featured by different positions of the Control Rods. Specifically, the case study for this work is the LFR benchmark, coordinated by the Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) [9].

The study is performed using the same pipeline adopted in [8]: the genetic algorithm is implemented by a C++ code that calls the multi-group diffusion module of the Fast REactor NEutronics/Thermal-hydraulics (FRENETIC) code to test each individual grid proposed comparing it with a reference solution computed with the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code. Serpent is also employed to generate the fine-group energy constants.

2. METHODOLOGY AND TOOLS

2.1. The genetic-based optimisation methodology

Genetic Algorithms belong to a broader class of optimization techniques known as Evolutionary Algorithms, which consist in meta-heuristic procedures able to solve complex optimization problems, identifying close-to-optimal solutions by mimicking natural evolutionary processes. The optimisation procedure begins with the generation of the initial population, i.e. in this case a set of few-group energy structures, which are initialised according to a random seed provided along with the setting parameters. The individuals belonging to the initial population are then ranked according to their performances, which are measured and quantified using the so-called fitness functions. The new generation is bred taking into account some genetic user-defined operators that allow to generate new solutions to explore and exploit the solution space while preserving the positive traits of the best performing individuals of the previous generation. These steps are iterated until one of the termination conditions is reached. The exploration and exploitation of the solution space are extremely important to obtain a successful optimisation of the problem, since the former allows to visit new regions of the search space, while the latter leverages the regions within the neighbourhood of good-performing individuals already spawn in previous generations.

As in biology, the individuals generated by the GA are represented by a unique chromosome structure containing all the genetic information characterising each individual. The chromosome representation (Fig. 1) employed in this paper was inherited from [7]. The individual karyotype is composed of two chromosome sets: the first one (γ_0) consists of a single chromosome with a single gene, describing the *number* of energy boundaries; the second set (γ_1) is polyploid, so it contains multiple chromosomes with the energy boundaries as alleles.

The definition of the physics-based fitness functions is a crucial step, as they actually identify the required properties of the solution space and affect the GA and the convergence of the search process. In this case as well, the set of FFs was carried over from [7], with the addition of two FFs addressing for the effective neutron life-time (Λ_{eff}) and the effective delayed neutron fraction (β_{eff}). Hence, the set of FFs involves the one referred to the power density,

$$f_P^I = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^J \left(\frac{P_j^I - P_j^{MC}}{P_j^{MC}} \right)^2}, \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Chromosome representation, where G is the number of internal energy boundaries, H is the number of groups defining the starting fine-energy grid, P is the number of arrays composing the γ_1 polyploid chromosome set, and M is an hyper-parameter defining the possible alleles [8].

the one for the flux

$$f_P^I = \sqrt{\sum_{g=1}^G \sum_{j=1}^J w_{g,i} \left(\frac{\Phi_{g,j}^I - \Phi_{g,j}^{MC}}{\Phi_{g,j}^{MC}} \right)^2}, \quad (2)$$

the one for the k_{eff}

$$f_k^I = |k^I - k^{MC}| \times 10^5, \quad (3)$$

and those related to the kinetic parameters

$$f_{\beta_{\text{eff}}}^I = |\beta_{\text{eff}}^I - \beta_{\text{eff}}^{MC}| \times 10^5, \quad f_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}^I = \frac{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}^I - \Lambda_{\text{eff}}^{MC}}{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}^{MC}} \times 10^2, \quad (4)$$

where I stands for the individual under examination, while G and J are associated to the the energy groups and the core assemblies, respectively. The parameters with the apex "MC" represent the reference values computed with the Monte Carlo code Serpent 2.

The weight appearing in Equation (2) is defined as the total importance $\phi\phi^\dagger/v$ [8]. In order to provide a unified criterion that simultaneously accounts for all the fitness functions computed for each individual, they are combined within a single joint FF, which is responsible for determining the ranking among the solutions explored along the optimisation process. The different nature among the FFs results in their substantial differences both in terms of orders of magnitude and in the range of variability. This makes it necessary to undergo linear scaling, which allows to normalize each FF value with respect to the dynamic minimum and maximum values of the FF itself.

$$h_L : f \rightarrow 1 + 99 \cdot \frac{f - \min_{\forall I \in E}(f^I)}{\max_{\forall I \in E}(f^I) - \min_{\forall I \in E}(f^I)}. \quad (5)$$

where f^I is a general fitness function associated to the individual I and E is the set of all already evaluated solutions.

For a single core configuration, the joint FF appears as

$$FF^I = h_L(f_k^I) \cdot h_L(f_P^I) \cdot h_L(f_\Phi^I) \cdot h_L(f_{\Lambda_{\text{eff}}}^I) \cdot h_L(f_\beta^I), \quad (6)$$

but since the three different reactor core configurations are going to be simultaneously considered, the effective joint FF is composed of 15 fitness functions (5 for each configuration), which is evaluated performing the product between them.

2.2. The Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code for fine-group constants generation

For each core configuration analysed, Serpent 2 was exploited to generate the reference figures of merit needed for the FF evaluation and the spatially homogenized fine-group constants (evaluated at isothermal conditions, having both the fuel and the coolant temperatures at 673 K). Since they are homogenised over the reactor heterogeneous regions, a compromise between the material discretization and the statistics was reached. The data are collapsed over a fine-group energy structure characterised by 30 energy groups, whose energy boundaries are extracted from the ECCO-33 grid and defined so that few groups are used to describe both the thermal and fast region due to statistical noise. The 30 fine-group structure represents the pool of the energy boundaries proposed by the GA.

2.3. The FRENETIC code for coarse energy structure testing

FRENETIC is a multiphysics computational tool featured by a neutronic (NE) and a thermal-hydraulic (TH) models, which are coupled together to provide a multiphysics description of liquid-metal cooled fast reactor cores characterized by hexagonal and closed assemblies. The code aims at separately or simultaneously solving the NE and TH models both in steady-state and time-dependent conditions, at the full-core level of the LFR under investigation.

The NE module of FRENETIC is exploited here to evaluate the individuals, i.e. coarser energy grids, proposed by the GA. Since the algorithm may investigate several hundreds of individuals for each configuration, the computational cost featuring each run needs to be reduced as much as possible. This aspect is dependent on several aspects, among them the axial discretization of the reactor assemblies, whose definition also strongly affects the accuracy of the FRENETIC outputs. The axial discretisation was selected considering the issues related to the material homogenization and the presence of optically thin regions that may affect the nodal solver of the NE module. On top of these aspects, the definition of the axial nodes is carried out ensuring that its performances are appropriate for all the three reactor configurations under investigation: this would make possible to perform a consistent comparison among the outputs of the GA and, furthermore, to potentially apply the optimization code to transient cases, considering that the reactor evolves between the configurations considered.

3. RESULTS

The three core configurations considered for the GA optimisation differ for the control rods (CRs) positions: fully withdrawn (CR_{out}), partially inserted (CR_{in0}) or fully inserted (CR_{in55}). The configuration CR_{in0} is obtained translating the CRs so that their absorbing region faces the fuel for a length of 28 cm.

The GA optimisations hyperparameters are listed in Table I. The minimum and maximum number of energy groups featuring the solution are defined *a priori* and are equal to 4 and 20, respectively. As better detailed in [8], the definition of the individuals guessed by the GA at the beginning of the optimisation process depends on an input string (seed) provided during the simulation set up. As the set of starting solutions may have an impact on the subsequent stochastic optimization process, it is reasonable to test a more than one seed, which we will refer to as "tribes": Boltzmann, Fermi and Henry.

The best individuals proposed by the GA show energy structures with more than 15 groups. Considering the maximum upper limit, it is clear that the GA tends to drive the solutions towards a relatively high number of energy groups, which might results in a counter-intuitive outcome, reminding that diffusion theory may behave poorly with optically thin groups.

An encouraging result is that similar convergence trends (see Figure 2) are observed across the different

Table I. Parameters for GA setup.

Selection method	Tournament selection	Tournament number	10
Tournament probability, p	0.2	Mutation probability	20 %
Elitism fraction	10 %	Crossover fraction	20 %
Individuals per generation	100		

tribes. resulting in energy structures that share many energy boundaries. It can be observed that the nature of the individuals making up the first population impacts on the evolutionary process of the algorithm. This aspect can get noticed by looking at the average joint FF peaks reached at the beginning of the optimization processes, for each tribe. As a consequence, the loss of some energy boundaries of the fine-grid is probably due to the individuals tested in this generational interval.

Figure 2. Convergence history of the average FF of each tribe, respectively normalized with respect to the maximum joint FF.

The interpretation of the convergence trend is also confirmed by the graphs in Figure 5, which represents both the positioning of the best individuals in the genealogical line, and the evolution of the solution space from the point of view of the energy boundaries considered by the GA. Indeed, it is possible to observe that within the first tens of generations, the potential associated with some energy boundaries decreases. In certain cases, those boundaries are permanently disregarded, whereas in others, they may eventually re-emerge, most likely as a result of the cross-over and mutation processes.

In Figure 4 some best individuals are depicted as a reference. The solutions proposed by the GA for the multi-configuration cases share many boundaries and only slightly deviate, in terms of both number of energy groups and energy boundaries, from those proposed by the single-configuration simulations, which have been conducted to identify potential variations in the behaviour of the genetic algorithm when more constraints are introduced. Among the cases, the algorithm seems to consistently provide a slightly finer discretization in the epithermal region, while energy boundaries in the neighbourhood of flux and power peaks are generally excluded.

This last aspect can be confirmed by Figure 3, which emphasises the low selection frequency of high-energy boundaries. The limited heterogeneity of the solutions may be a symptom of the constraints introduced by the need to identify a common structure for the three different core configurations. However, this may be also due to the limited number of energy boundaries available in the pool of the starting energy grid. Further studies may be performed to investigate this aspect by providing a finer initial grid, with the aim of testing the consistency of the GA.

Figure 3. Distribution of individuals per number of energy groups at the last generation for each tribe (left) and distribution of individuals per each energy group boundaries through the whole evolution, for each tribe (right). Group boundaries are numbered from the most to the least energetic ones.

Figure 4. Best individuals of single-configuration cases (left) and multi-configuration ones (right) against the power produced as a function of incident neutron energy. The dots represent the best individuals energy boundaries for, respectively, the different core layouts and seeds.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The specific aim of this study was identifying a common energy group structure for three different core layouts of the NEA LFR benchmark with a genetic algorithm. For this purpose, 3D Serpent 2 models were built for each core configuration, and the starting energy group libraries were generated, based on a fine energy structure composed by 30 groups, whose boundaries were extracted by the ECCO-33 group structure. The Monte Carlo code was exploited to retrieve some relevant reference quantities. Then, a FRENETIC neutronic model was defined for each core configuration, and some preliminary simulations were performed to test the starting fine energy grid. The Genetic Algorithm exploited a proper set of physics-based fitness functions. Each core-configuration was first tested individually, as a frame of reference. The results showed that the constraints related to the three configurations somehow limit the solution space when the GA is required to find a solution shared across the three different core-configuration under investigation. As a consequence, simulation outputs, although based on different initial seeds, tend to exhibit a minimal variation one from the other, with the exception of few energy boundaries.

Figure 5. Evolution of the individuals of the single - configuration (top) and multi-configuration (bottom) optimisation process, per each tribe. The vertical lines represent the starting fine energy structure, the red dots the individuals in each generation, the white stars indicate the best individuals energy boundaries while the blue stars the best individual

Further investigation will be conducted using a finer reference energy grid, hence providing the GA with a broader range of options. Moreover, the best individuals proposed by the GA are characterized by a relatively high number of energy groups, which, in the context of exploiting these solutions in transient or multiphysics simulations, may lead to cumbersome computational costs. To address this issue, the chromosomal parameter may be modified by introducing some fitness operator penalising the individuals featured by a large number of energy groups, unless the addition of further groups provide a considerable gain in accuracy.

Further development of this study may involve the optimisation of the energy structure of a multiphysics case, hence accounting for the feedback, and the axial discretization of the reactor core geometry, in order to try to reduce the error introduced by material homogenization during the definition of the neutronic model.

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